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Abstract

A noise injection Dicke Microwave Radiometer employing a digital signal processor has been designed, developed, and flight tested. The principles of operation, along with results of laboratory and flight tests on this system are presented.

SummaryBackground

The use of digital signal processing and control techniques in radiometer design has many potential advantages over the analog approach. These include reduction in the effects of Dicke ripple, real time operator or computer adjusted loop algorithm, higher order responses, and a reduction in cabling, which is very advantages in multiple radiometer array applications. There are problems, however, associated with incorporating a digital signal processor within the radiometer loop.⁴ In order to resolve these issues, a C-band radiometer was designed which could be used either with analog or digital processing so that a performance comparison could be made. This radiometer design is the first known to utilize digital processing within the radiometer control loop (fig. 1). The performance of both the digital and analog systems were flight tested on a NASA P-3 aircraft. The purpose of this paper is to show that a radiometer employing a digital filter and control system with the same loop response as an analog system has performance characteristics equal or superior to that of the analog system.

A block diagram is shown in figure 2 of the digital signal processor incorporated into the existing radiometer. The integrator and other analog processes of the radiometer which normally occur after the correlator were replaced by the digital processor. The digital processor samples the analog signal output of the correlator, performs the loop algorithm, and controls the noise injection and Dicke switching process.

After the signal is sampled, the digital word is operated on by the microprocessor algorithm. The processing algorithm selected is an accumulator which results in a first order closed loop radiometer response. The output of this algorithm controls the injected noise by loading the loop output into a down counter clocked at 2^N-1 times the sample rate (N is the number of bits in the output word loaded to the counter). The injected noise power is controlled by gating on the noise source when the value of the counter word is greater than zero and gating it off when the value reaches zero.

Flight Test

The C-band radiometer was flown using both the analog and digital processing configuration during missions off the coast of Georgia and over the Gulf Stream boundary. These missions were conducted primarily to evaluate the ability of an L-band-PRT-5 infrared radiometer instrument compliment to determine ocean salinity and ocean surface temperature. These measured parameters (from L-band & PRT-5) were then used to compute the expected C-band brightness temperature for

comparison with the measured C-band brightness temperature.

The comparison is shown in figure 3 for a typical flight across the Gulf Stream, for the analog radiometer, the correlation is excellent. The digital processing radiometer comparison is shown in figure 4. Again, there is very good correlation. The discrepancy in figure 4 between the measured and modelled data as the aircraft crosses the Gulf Stream boundary (700 to 1200 second into flight line) is due to cloud coverage which caused errors in the PRT-5 infrared measurement and is not due to problems within the radiometer. Figure 5 shows the analog and digital measured brightness temperature plotted against their respective modelled brightness temperature. The increased fluctuations in figure 5b are due to the cloud cover problem mentioned earlier. The scatter plot for the analog processing radiometer appears linear with a slope greater than one. It has not yet been determined if this is due to parameters not included in the model (surface conditions, atmospheric corrections, etc.) which were encountered during the analog flight lines or if it is a peculiarity of the analog radiometer. The digital processing radiometer also seems to respond linearly over this range of brightness temperature.

One very important aspect of the radiometer's performance is the uncertainty in the estimate of the antenna temperature, ΔT . The fluctuation (uncertainty) in the measurement should be essentially the same for both the digital and analog processing radiometer.⁴ Since the flight data satisfies the assumption of a Gaussian distributed random variable, the hypothesis of equal ΔT for analog and digital techniques can be tested using the test statistic:²

$$F = \frac{\sigma^2_{MAX}}{\sigma^2_{MIN}}$$

where F is a random variable having the F distribution with N-1 and N-1 degrees of freedom (N = independent samples).

Using the values of ΔT and F calculated from flight data, it can be claimed that the ΔT of the digital radiometer is less than or equal to that of the analog system. Further, it can be shown that the claim of equal or improved digital ΔT is correct at the 95% confidence level even if the actual ΔT of the radiometers differ by only 3.5%.

The above test results indicate that the performance of the digital processing radiometer was at least equivalent to that of the original analog system over the range of brightness temperatures encountered (approximately 104K - 110K). Although further tests are required to compare the linearity of the digital and analog systems over a large range of brightness temperature, it appears from the test results so far that the digital processing technique is a viable alternative to the analog approach.

List of References

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Figure 1. Digital signal processing radiometer.

Figure 2. Block diagram of digital processing radiometer.

Figure 3. Analog C-band radiometer flight data.

Figure 4. Digital C-band radiometer flight data.

a. Analog

b. Digital

Figure 5. Scatter plot comparing C-band radiometer with predicted brightness temperature.